

MEASURES TO INCREASE THE SOCIAL ACTIVITY OF YOUTH IN SOCIETY AND THEIR IMPORTANCE.

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Abstract: The article analyzes the process of socialization of the individual and the reforms being implemented in the field of increasing the social activity of young people, and discusses the importance of the reforms.

Keywords: socialization, social activism, process, reform, youth, social development, education

The process by which an individual acquires the behavioral patterns, norms, and values necessary for a successful life in a particular society is called socialization. The question of the individual's activity or passivity in this process is a controversial issue in science. The process of socialization is the integration of an individual into a social system, the assimilation of its social norms and rules, the accumulation of values, knowledge and skills that allow him to enter the social environment and successfully function in society. Socialization is the process of an individual's adaptation to the world around them. Once a person is born, if they can adapt to it, they can live in human society. This adaptation process can be very complex. But, ultimately, each person adapts to the social environment. According to another theory, socialization is "a set of social processes that allow the individual to master and reproduce a certain system of knowledge, norms and values, which ensures the functioning of the individual as a full-fledged member of society" (I.S. Kon) [1]. Socialization is therefore the process by which a person acquires the skills necessary to live a full life in society [2]. Unlike other living beings whose behavior is biologically determined, humans, as biosocial beings, require a process of socialization. Initially, the socialization of an individual usually occurs within the family, and then outside it. Primary socialization continues from birth to the formation of a mature personality[3]. Primary socialization is very important for a child, because it is the basis for the rest of the entire socialization process. Since we are historically among the nations that value national values, the socialization processes of our youth are multifaceted. In our country, great work is being done to increase the social activity of young people. The main focus is on education. In the meantime, psychologists and sociologists working with young people are improving the socialization process of children in the family, taking into account the family environment, and are showing effective results. The most active part of civil society is precisely young

people. For example, young people have a strong tendency to introduce innovative projects and technologies in various fields, to bring new ideas and knowledge to society, and to build their own lives[3]. From this perspective, the youth of Uzbekistan, as the owners of today and tomorrow, are the main strategic resource in building the foundation of a prosperous life in our country. The country's progress on the path of democratic renewal and the pace of development largely depend on the position and activity of young people in the socio-political life of society. Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev emphasized that "...we need to talk more with our youth, listen to their hearts, understand their pain, provide practical assistance in solving their problems, and in this regard, we need to pay special attention to working with unorganized youth" [4]. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Youth Policy", adopted on September 14, 2016, clearly defines the main directions of socio-economic, legal and organizational measures in this regard. The law states that state youth policy in Uzbekistan envisages "creating conditions for the social formation, development of intellectual, creative and other potential of young people"[5]. In these processes, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, which unites the youth of our country around creative ideas, is playing an important role. In the system of comprehensive social development areas, the issue of providing modern education and upbringing to young people and their social support is of particular importance due to its acuteness and relevance. After all, it is known from history that in every era, enlightenment has been the impetus for the prosperity of society and the prosperity of the country. Therefore, now the issue of transferring the saying of our wise people "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave" to our practical life activities, and implementing the principle of continuity of education and upbringing in our country is rising to the level of state policy. Over the past three years, large-scale measures have been implemented to bring the education system to the level of modern democratic countries and further enhance the role of youth in our society as a leading force for development. It is worth noting that it is difficult for a state and society that has not defined the idea and prospects of development, is devoid of spiritual foundations, and most importantly, has not found a way to please young citizens and imagine a prosperous future. The state's attitude towards young people is one of the indicators of the level of development, openness, and forward movement of society. Therefore, the issue of youth is of particular importance in state policies aimed at strengthening society and supporting civic initiatives. In the era of deepening reforms, it is precisely the youth that is capable of overcoming various obstacles and giving strength to our

country's steps towards development. In the context of globalization, along with new opportunities for the development of our society, non-spiritual threats have also emerged, and today there is a strong need to further improve national spirituality and the promotion of the national idea in line with the requirements of the times. In this process, the issue of youth is emerging as an important factor in ensuring the connection between the present and the future in our country, preserving national identity. Our President put forward a proposal to establish new cultural and recreational parks on the basis of public-private partnership, to transform them into modern youth centers that will serve to establish a healthy lifestyle among the younger generation, and to promote a reading culture. It was emphasized that no reforms can be implemented in our country without an understanding of the national idea, national identity, and a sense of patriotism. It is worth noting that the democratic reforms being implemented in our country today at a completely new qualitative stage are aimed, among other ambitious tasks, at the comprehensive and consistent implementation of the noble goals, aspirations, ideas, and most importantly, innovative ideas of young people. In turn, our youth, who are able to make the most progressive principles and values of democracy the guiding principles of their activities, will have the high status of being the pillars of our country's development. In general, in today's politics, consistent economic reforms are seen as a component of social progress in our country. This implies further improving the mechanisms for educating young people who are intellectually mature and creative today, possessing modern knowledge and skills, and are able to take responsibility for the worthy future of our country. All the conditions created in our country for young people to realize their potential and aspirations will serve to comprehensively educate them in the future, to shape them into competitive personnel, and to contribute to the prosperity of the country and peace in the homeland with their progressive ideas and initiatives.

References:

1. Социализация//Большой психологический словарь.-Олма-пресс,2004
2. Andreeva E. Ijtimoiy psixologiya -M.:Аспект Пресс,2003.-С.267
3. Козина Е.С. Развитие инновационного потенциала в рамках молодежной политики. Сборник статей. - М.: Директ -Медиа, 2013. - С. 29.
4. Mirziyoyev SH.M. Qonun ustuvorligi va inson manfaatlarini ta'minlash - yurt taraqqiyoti va xalq farovonligining garovi. - T.: O'zbekiston, 2017. - B. 23.
5. "Yoshlarga oid davlat siyosati to'g'risida" gi O'zbekiston Respublikasi Qonuni. 2016 yil 14 sentabr // O'zbekiston Respublikasi qonun hujjatlari ma'lumotlari milliy bazasi - Lex.Uz. <http://lex.uz/>

6. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “Ёшлар- келажагимиз” Давлат дастури тўғ‘рисида” ги Фармони. 2018 йил 27 июн // Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари маълумотлари миллий базаси - Lex.Uz. <http://lex.uz/>

7. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyevning O‘zbekiston yoshlariga bayram tabrigi // Xalq so‘zi, 2019 yil 1 iyul №133(73-63) 9. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Mahallalarda yoshlar bilan ishlash tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish chora-tadbirlari to‘g‘risida”gi qarori yuzasidan ma‘lumot. Manba: <http://yoshlar.gov.uz>.

